

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*} Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)⁸ Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)⁶ Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder: Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anwar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anwar since 2020: 312.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne,

Vic 3056, Australia

[\(engr.anowar@yahoo.com\)](mailto:engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Contact

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director and Founder, since 2020

Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre

School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne,

Vic 3056, Australia; 21 May 2025; Mobile Phone: +880-1788396264; Email:

engr.anowar@yahoo.com

Key functions of job

- Master, PhD, and Postdoc supervision in textile engineering, defence engineering, and law
- Peer review in textile technology, defence technology, and law
- Research and development in textile, defence, and law
- Publication in textile, defence, and law
- Administration in textile, defence, and law
- Life time founder director (2022-) (M. A. Hossain, 2023g, 2023h)(M. A. Hossain, 2023au; Hossain, 2025a, 2025b, 2025c)
- Scholarly and royalty founder director
- Contributed and self-invested to increase the brand value of RMIT University by research and publication in 2020-2025 (M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g).

Income type

- Life time income
- Life time royalty income

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anwar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anwar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

- Royalty income after the death of Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain (2022-)

Non-paid salary per annum (final year)

60,000USD

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Category of office time

Ancillary and part-time/casual

Name of organization

Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre

School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia

Nature of organization

- ✓ Research and development
- ✓ Defence
- ✓ Textile engineering
- ✓ Technical textiles
- ✓ Law

Nature of Job

- Practice of textile engineering and director.
- Practice of defence scientist and director.
- Practice of barrister and director.
- Sole fund investment and management since 6 July 2022.
- Sole scholarly investment and management since 6 July 2022.
- Life time director of the textile, defence, and law research centre.

Alignment of Master degree by research/thesis, PhD degree by research/thesis, and Postdoc by research/thesis, backgrounds matching, self-interests, and excellency in research and development(M. A. Hossain, 2023au)

- Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is inviting PhD and Postdoc researchers in different backgrounds of PhD applicants to make the right PhD and Postdoc alignment with

Barrister (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

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personal profile under consultation with the applicants who are interested to pursue research in PhD and Postdoc in Textile Engineering, Defence Engineering, and Law.

- Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is inviting CV and PhD thesis of professors/supervisors/scientists/consultants for PhD and Postdoc supervision in different backgrounds of candidates to make the right PhD and Postdoc alignment with personal profile under consultation with the supervisors who are interested to supervise the relevant research in PhD and Postdoc. The brief CV bank of professors will be advance stored and scholarly analyzed for the right allotment of PhD supervisors in the relevant expertise.

Profile of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (M. A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2018) (A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b; Hossain, Islam, et al., 2018; A. Hossain & A. Samanta, 2019; A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2018; Hossain, Samanta, Bhaumik, et al., 2018; Hossain, Samanta, NS, et al., 2018; A. Hossain et al., 2019; Hossain, 2009, 2010b, 2010c, 2015a, 2019a, 2019c, 2019d; M. A. Hossain, 2021a, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023ap; M. A. Hossain et al., 2019; M. A. Hossain & A. K. Samanta, 2019) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024a) (M. A. Hossain, 2023aj, 2023am, 2023bj, 2023ch, 2023ci) (Anowar Hossain, 2016; A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2023; Hossain, 17 May 2023, 2010a, 2015b, 2015c, 2018, 2019b; M. A. Hossain, 2020, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2022a, 2022b, 2022c; Md Anowar Hossain, 2022; M. A. Hossain, 2023a, 2023b, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e, 2023f, 2023h, 2023i, 2023j, 2023k, 2023l, 2023m, 2023n, 2023o, 2023p, 2023q, 2023r, 2023s, 2023t, 2023u, 2023v, 2023w, 2023x, 2023y, 2023z, 2023aa, 2023ab, 2023ac, 2023ad, 2023ae, 2023af, 2023ag, 2023ah, 2023ai, 2023aj, 2023ak, 2023al, 2023am, 2023an, 2023ao, 2023ap, 2023aq, 2023ar, 2023as, 2023at, 2023au, 2023av, 2023aw, 2023ax, 2023ay, 2023az, 2023ba, 2023bb, 2023bc, 2023bd, 2023be, 2023bf, 2023bg, 2023bh, 2023bi, 2023bj, 2023bk, 2023bl, 2023bm, 2023bn; M. A. Hossain, 2023a; M. A. Hossain, 2023bo, 2023bp, 2023bq, 2023br, 2023bs, 2023bt; M. A. Hossain, 2023b; M. A. Hossain, 2023bu, 2023bv, 2023bw; M. A. Hossain, 2023c, 2023d, 2023e; M. A. Hossain, 2023bx, 2023by, 2023bz, 2023ca, 2023cb, 2023cc, 2023cd; M. A. Hossain, 2023f, 2023g; M. A. Hossain, 2023ce, 2023cf, 2023cg, 2023ch, 2023ci, 2023cj, 2023ck; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024b, 2024c, 2024d, 2024e, 2024f, 2024g, 2024h, 2024i, 2024j, 2024k, 2024l, 2024m, 2024n, 2024o, 2024p, 2024q, 2024r, 2024s, 2024t, 2024u, 2024v, 2024w, 2024x, 2024y; Md.. Anowar Hossain, 2024; Md. Anowar Hossain, 2024z; Hossain, 2025d, 2025e, 2025f, 2025g; Nobel Nominee Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, 2025)

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2880-6287>

Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Engr-Md-Hossain>

www.linkedin.com/in/engr-md-anowar-hossain-PhD-RMIT

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Barrister (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
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 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
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 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder; Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
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 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 312.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD² in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD²
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 312.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
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Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

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Nobel Nominee Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
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 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
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Barrister (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Nobel Nominée Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.), Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology
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 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).
 Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
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**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

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Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 312.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
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- Hossain, M. A. (2023bq). *Presentation on Camouflage textiles with technical coloration incorporating illumination under multidimensional combat backgrounds, PhD student: 3820066, RMIT University;* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048> <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29042.48322>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8146048>
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Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.)
 Postdoc² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
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 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
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Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

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Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

- RTP Stipend Scholarship. . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.27226.72648>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8260252>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023by). *Reporting to Victorian Ombudsman for compliance investigation of unethical PhD suspension, unethical scholarship suspension, psychologist bullying of school administration and cancellation of PhD enrolment of Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD ID: 3820066 under the official act of hidden life threatening and killing conspiracy to kill PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain when few complaint letters against Professor Dr. Rajiv Padhye were submitted to the whole concern of RMIT University including Professor (Dr.) Alec Cameron, Vice Chancellor, RMIT University; Professor Calum Drummond, Deputy Vice Chancellor, Research and Innovation, RMIT University; Dr. Scott Mayson, Associate dean, Research and Innovation; Dr. Andrea Eckersley, HDR coordinator, School of Fashion & Textiles; Professor (Dr.) Lijing Wang, Senior Supervisor and Emeritus Professor (Dr.) Robert Shanks, Associate supervisor, School of Fashion & Textiles, RMIT University when PhD candidate contributed for 42 month duration (full time) PhD candidature under nonpaid scholarship of one year duration under Australian Government RTP Stipend Scholarship.* . <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31999.79522>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8315574>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023bz). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of City University, Dhaka, Bangladesh, Year 2006-2010 (academic), 2017-2019 (professional).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.19275.98087>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8286941>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ca). *Research and publication output of Md. Anowar Hossain on Textile Engineering under affiliation of University of Calcutta, Kolkata, India, 2013-2015.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12565.09440>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15068327>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cb). *Self-declared certificate on PhD (Fashion & Textiles).* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30457.65123>;
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10978165>
- Self-declared certificate on Professor (Textile Engineering), (2023cc). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36591.82084>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275164>
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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8275143>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023f). *Services for crime in higher education & quality enhancement in an international platform.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26551.70569>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8278997>

<p>Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.) Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD² Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh), MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh); Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process, color engg), applied law & criminology Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)* Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)* Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia</p> <p>International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law, PhD, & Postdoc): R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech, MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; ancillary (defence research organization of army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission; applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court, international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile, defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur), Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)</p>	<p>Chief Director & Founder: Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg; Former Assisit. Registrar (Exam); Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd. Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Assisit. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 312.01.12.25; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; Contact: engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264 Biodata: http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1</p>	
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- Hossain, M. A. (2023cf). Simultaneous Thermoregulated and Sensorial effect of Smart Textiles with Artificial Composite Phase Change Materials (CPCM) incorporated with Carbon Nano Conductive Materials for special workers and extreme weather conditions; Accepted in Advanced Material Research (2019-2020). *School of Fashions and Textiles, RMIT University, Victoria 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8112357>; <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32289.79204>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cg). *Specialized services and payment rate of Professor (Dr.) Md. Anowar Hossain*. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21820.00643>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10360742>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ch). Spectral simulation and materials design for camouflage textiles coloration against materials of multidimensional combat backgrounds in visible and near infrared spectrums. *MRS Communications* <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43579-023-00344-3>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023ci). UV–Visible–NIR camouflage textiles with natural plant based natural dyes on natural fibre against woodland combat background for defence protection. *Scientific Reports*. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-31725-2>
- Hossain, M. A. (2023cj). *Video reporting for removal of executive suspension and reporting to withdraw of executive suspension when Australian schooling compliance was breached for my PhD candidature in PhD school through the official act of hidden life threatening of PhD candidate, Md. Anowar Hossain (Part-01)*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.33752.88325>; <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8154453>; <https://youtu.be/86cxLN3Z9ro>
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<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17601.12648;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14282484>

Hossain, M. A. (2024b). *Australian Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist asked 100000 Australian penalty unit to Hon Mark Dreyfus KC MP, Australian Attorney General/law minister of Australian Government.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14776.72967;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10556279>

Hossain, M. A. (2024c). *Coalesced the syllabus and course structures in textile engineering and relevant courses in the eighteen years duration academic and professional journey of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist from 2006 to 2024.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21803.66082;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13888294>

Hossain, M. A. (2024d). *Cyber securities for protection of cyber-crimes.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14367.98729;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841349>

Hossain, M. A. (2024e). *A follow-up letter to The Hon Jason Clare MP, Education Minister, Australia for the conspiracy of life-threatening and PhD harassment in Australian PhD school.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18413.19685;>

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Hossain, M. A. (2024f). *Journal Peer Review Report of PhD Thesis of "Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist" on "Camouflage Textiles with Technical Coloration Incorporating Illumination under Multidimensional Combat Backgrounds"* School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com).

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36270.32328;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13182515>

Hossain, M. A. (2024g). *Letter to Nobel committee for Nobel prize in camouflage physics.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36807.51367;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842435>

Hossain, M. A. (2024h). *Letter to Nobel Committee for Nobel Prize in Peace.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35129.79208;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842361>

Hossain, M. A. (2024i). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain is searching research fund for surviving in research profession and self-learning.* R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22732.42888;>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13997939>

Hossain, M. A. (2024j). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is asking to Ms. Nardia Simpson, Australian High Commissioner for approving*

Barrister (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.).
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD³ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
 MTech Textile Engg (CU, India), BSc Textile Engg (CU, Bangladesh);
 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder: Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
 Chief Editor & Founder, Journal of Dr. Anowar, Melbourne, Australia
 Lecturer (study leave & research), Dept. of Textile Engg, City University, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Prof. & Head, Dept. of Garments & Textile Engg, BCMC College of Engg
 & Tech; University of Rajshahi & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assis. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assis. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 312.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

the extension of Australian Student VISA for legal and ethical claiming to Australian court under the ethical support of Minister of home affairs, foreign affairs and education.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.14584.05126;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14699107>

Hossain, M. A. (2024k). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking income support and/or salary, free of cost legal support and/or legal funding, and free of cost safety to Mr. Mohammed Shahabuddin, President; and Nobel Winner Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus, Chief Advisor of Bangladesh to continue PhD schooling at RMIT University, Melbourne, Australia.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22210.80326;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14837268>

Hossain, M. A. (2024l). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is seeking support of 'free of cost google drive (2TB) access' to Pichai Sundararajan, Chief Executive Officer, Google against the e-mail address of engranowar06@gmail.com.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.28761.94568;>

Hossain, M. A. (2024m). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist is self-nominating for 'global excellence award' at Functional Textiles and Clothing (FTC), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT), Delhi, India under the category of 'Leadership in Research' and/or 'Emerging Innovator' under the invitation of FTC team, IIT, Delhi, India.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36325.61929;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14213757>

Hossain, M. A. (2024n). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is asking an exemption of visa fees for the 'Australian global talent permanent residence visa (subclass 858)' under the Australian migration act 45C (c), 1958 and 500.211,1994.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25869.14560;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12754106>

Hossain, M. A. (2024o). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of '2100–4200-point policy for the impact factor to certify researcher for PhD degree by Research' and 'PhD in PhD'.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35642.20167;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12604715>

Hossain, M. A. (2024p). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist is the first inventor of a 1150–2300-point policy to certify or review a research manuscript or thesis for publication R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia; engr.anowar@yahoo.com.*

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30482.88003;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12735576>

Hossain, M. A. (2024q). *Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Calcutta for*

his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20869.15843>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10842021>

Hossain, M. A. (2024r). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is asking 'honorary doctorate degree' to the Vice Chancellor of University of Dhaka for his contribution of PhD harassment at RMIT University. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia (engr.anowar@yahoo.com). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.36388.08325>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841964>

Hossain, M. A. (2024s). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is searching a good-looking lady for his marriage, a requirement of RMIT PhD school.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13112.97282>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12747830>

Hossain, M. A. (2024t). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1100–2200-point policy for the impact factor to admit/appoint researcher position for Master degree by research. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.12531.75048>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16628548>

Hossain, M. A. (2024u). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 1250–2500-point policy for the impact factor to certify university designation and university promotion from lecturer to professor.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13177.68968>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11183360>

Hossain, M. A. (2024v). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the first inventor of 7050–14100-point policy for the impact factor or ranking of an international standard University. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25604.13447>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814275>

Hossain, M. A. (2024w). Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist is the inventor of 10-point policy to elect the democratic leaders all over the world. R. U. School of Fashion and Textiles, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056, Australia

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10662617>

Hossain, M. A. (2024x). Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist represented his photographic memories of profession in textile engineering and casual life journey.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32669.69609>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10449995>

Hossain, M. A. (2024y). Research services, journal peer reviews, and editorial support of Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD; Defence Scientist.

<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.15157.90080>;

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13142538>

Barrister (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Law), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

Nobel Nominee Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Defence Scientist (Dr.), Barrister (Dr.),
 Postdoc⁴ Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc³ & PhD⁵ in Law (RMIT, Australia),
 Postdoc² Tech (RMIT, Australia), Postdoc¹ Textile Tech (Australia & UK), PhD^{2*}
 Textile Tech (RMIT, Australia), PhD¹ Textile Tech (CU, India & JU, Bangladesh),
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 Professor and Engineer (R&D) in textile tech (technical textiles, dyeing & process,
 color engg), applied law & criminology
 Australian government award winner (RTP stipend scholarship, 2020)*
 Indian government award winner (best researcher award, IRS awards-2025)*
 Nobel nominee of vice chancellor (2021), RMIT University, Australia
**International Professor & Research Consultant (Textile Engineering, Defence, Law,
 PhD, & Postdoc):** R & D in dyeing & finishing (textile engg); textile & chemical
 processing; technical textiles; defence textiles & materials; professor of BSc, MSc, BTech,
 MTech, MPhil, PhD & Postdoc in textile tech; **ancillary** (defence research organization of
 army, navy, air force and police; public service, crime, crisis & textile commission;
 applied law; criminology; human rights; judge court, high court, supreme court,
 international court, ministry, minister, president, governor, king of any country; textile,
 defence, law, education, home ministry, parliament, government of any country; crime
 analysis & reporting, quality in higher education, research & publication, entrepreneur),
 Postdoc & PhD in applied law, legal consultant & barrister (Dr.)

Chief Director & Founder, Textile, Defence & Law Research Centre; RMIT, Australia
 Chief Professor, Prof. Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain's Knowledge Industry, Australia
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 Former Lecturer & Head, Dept. of Textile Engg, Former Assist. Registrar (Exam);
 Newcastle University College, University of Chittagong & BTEB, Bangladesh
 Ex-CEO, Bangladesh Textile & Fashion, Nikurja-2, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Coordinator (product developer, textile printing & color engg), Gothic Design Ltd.
 Viyellatex Group, Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Assist. Merchandiser, Best Exchange Buying & Fashion, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Dyeing Officer (research & development), Mascom Composite Ltd., Radix Ltd,
 Gazipur, Dhaka, Bangladesh
 Former Chairman & Member, examination committee, University of Chittagong and
 University of Rajshahi, Bangladesh
 Trained from India; Australia; Germany & Bangladesh; ITC-UNCTAD/WTO, Geneva
Research address of Dr. Anowar since 2020: 512.01.12.25; School of Fashion and
 Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, VIC 3056,
 Australia; **Contact:** engr.anowar@yahoo.com; +8801788396264
Biodata: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.18182.34883/1>

Hossain, M. A. (2024). *Seeking VISA extension, legal support, legal costs, legal insurance support, accommodation costs, fooding costs, personal safety, PhD compensation award of Australian Government, PhD compensation award of RMIT University, PhD certificate, PhD mark sheets or academic transcript and job offer letter to Australian Home affairs.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34569.04960;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13822693>

Hossain, M. A. (2024z). *A self-understanding of Professor Dr. Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, Scientist about Bangladeshi Nobel laureate Professor Dr. Muhammad Yunus and law implementation of Bangladesh Government.*
<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.26912.35846;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10461097>

Hossain, M. A. (2025a). *Invitation of law researchers in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30060.63369;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16959326>

Hossain, M. A. (2025b). *Invitation of legal client for legal service to individual and/or organization.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.13073.70249;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16956497>

Hossain, M. A. (2025c). *Invitation of researchers in textile engineering in Master by thesis, PhD by thesis, and Postdoc by thesis.* <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.17215.57765;>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16960861>

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Professor (Dr.) Engr. Md. Anowar Hossain, PhD & Postdoc (Textile Engineering), RMIT, Australia

Cite: Md. Anowar Hossain; Textile, Defence, and Law Research Centre; School of Fashion and Textiles, RMIT University, 25 Dawson Street, Brunswick, Melbourne, Vic 3056, Australia; (engr.anowar@yahoo.com)

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